

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

García, S., Boullosa-Falces, D., Sanz, D. S., Trueba, A., & Gomez-Solaetxe, M. A. (2024). *Artificial-intelligence-model to optimize biocide dosing in seawater-cooled industrial process applications considering environmental, technical, energetic, and economic aspects*. **Biofouling**, 40(5–6), 366–376. This is an Accepted Manuscript of an article published by Taylor & Francis in **Biofouling** on 10 Jun 2024, available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/08927014.2024.2363241>

Artificial-intelligence-model to optimize biocide dosing in seawater-cooled industrial process applications considering environmental, technical, energetic, and economic aspects.

Sergio García, David Boullosa-Falces, David S. Sanz, Alfredo Trueba & Miguel Angel Gomez-Solaetxe

1
2
3
4 **Graphical abstract**
5

6 **Abstract**
7

8
9
10 This research introduces an Artificial Intelligence (AI) based model designed to
11 concurrently optimize energy supply management, biocide dosing, and maintenance
12 scheduling for heat exchangers. This optimization considers energetic, technical,
13 economic, and environmental considerations. The impact of biofilm on heat exchangers
14 is assessed, revealing a 41% reduction in thermal efficiency and a 113% increase in flow
15 frictional resistance of the fluid compared to the initial state. Consequently, the pump's
16 power consumption, required to maintain hydraulic conditions, rises by 9%. The newly
17 developed AI model detects the point at which the heat exchanger's performance begins
18 to decline due to accumulating dirt, marking day 44 of experimentation as the threshold
19 to commence the antifouling biocide dosing. Leveraging this AI model to monitor heat
20 exchanger efficiency represents an innovative approach to optimizing antifouling biocide
21 dosing and reduce the environmental impact stemming from industrial plants.
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29

30 **Keywords:** Artificial Intelligence, Energy-saving, Seawater, Biofilm, Heat exchanger,
31 Statistical algorithm.
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

1. Introduction

The thermal plants production procedures are having a gradual increase in the incorporation of AI analytics with the goal of amplifying the security, reliability and overall efficiency. Operational analytics arise as a central element in addressing these complex challenges. These analytic solutions step into the spotlight by pre-emptively predicting possible disturbances in procedures, assessing the attributes of processes, recognizing instances of equipment biofouling and inadequacies, foreseeing equipment breakdowns, overseeing emissions, and even predicting the onset of pipe corrosion (Gaudio et al., 2021).

Open recirculating cooling water is a commonly employed method in the process industry to refrigerate the heat produced during industrial processes (Al-Bloushi et al., 2020). Heat exchangers are extensively utilized for this purpose in both maritime and industrial settings that involve the transfer of energy between two fluids (Gudmundsson, Palsson, Palsson, & Lalot, 2016). Water is essential for the growth and survival of society, but it also poses significant challenges in this and various other domains. The natural growth of micro/macroorganisms (freshwater/seawater) on submerged surfaces can cause negative impacts on various industries, such as marine transport (e.g. ships, vessels), offshore structures (e.g. oil platforms, aquaculture cages), water purification plants (e.g. filters, pipelines, valves, tanks), and desalination processes. These impacts can result in economic losses, environmental harm, and health risks of industrial activities (Chan & Wong, 2010; Silva et al., 2019).

Marine biofilm refers to the buildup of marine microorganisms, animals, and plants on surfaces that are submerged in seawater (Hu, Xie, Ma, & Zhang, 2020). Marine biofilm can have significant effects on major coastal engineering equipment, such as tidal power plants and nuclear power plants, by blocking pipelines that transport seawater and reducing heat exchange efficiency (Brzozowska et al., 2014; Xie, Pan, Ma, & Zhang, 2019). The accumulation of biofilm on heat transfer surfaces is a complicated process that involves both physical and chemical reactions happening at the same time. The severity of the biofilm depends on several factors, including the nature of stream media and fouling substance, concentration, the temperature of the surface, flow velocity and flow structure, and surface material and roughness (Demirskiy, Kapustenko, Arsenyeva, Matsegora, & Pugach, 2018).

1
2
3
4 The build-up of unwanted biofilm on process equipment and heat exchanger surfaces can
5 have a considerable negative effect, as it can greatly reduce their working efficiency and
6 cause operational issues (Sundar et al., 2020). Specifically, heat exchanger fouling refers
7 to the accumulation of particles to heat transfer surfaces, leading to a decrease in the
8 overall efficiency of heat transfer in the heat exchangers (Olufade & Simonson, 2018).
9 This can also hinder fluid flow, corrodes the surfaces, and introduce impurities to the fluid
10 being processed. The impacts of fouling on heat and process industries can lead to
11 significant financial burdens. These include the need to install additional extended
12 surfaces, increased fuel consumption, production losses resulting from unplanned
13 fouling-related shutdowns, and the cost of maintenance to remove fouling deposits using
14 chemicals and mechanical anti-fouling devices (Sundar et al., 2020). The economic losses
15 due to biofilm adhesion have shown that in highly industrialized countries, the
16 incremental cost due to biofouling can amount to approximately 0.25% of their gross
17 domestic product (Demirskiy et al., 2018). As a result, managing biofilm is a unique and
18 intricate issue that varies across different industries. It involves finding ways to prevent
19 or eliminate unwanted organisms that accumulate on surfaces, which calls for the creation
20 of new technologies and techniques to reduce negative effects (Fitridge, Dempster,
21 Guenther, & De Nys, 2012).
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32

33 Several techniques have been employed to prevent biofilm formation. The traditional
34 methods include physical measures like mechanical displacement of biofilm biomass,
35 flow inversion physical treatment (Eguía, Trueba, Río-Calonge, Girón, & Bielva, 2008),
36 and chemical cleaning. However, chemical cleaning requires high chemical
37 concentrations that can accelerate the surface's degradation due to the use of harsh
38 reagents (Rice et al., 2021). Biocides can also be used to inactivate or inhibit biofilm-
39 forming bacteria. Biological control involves using mechanisms within the
40 microorganisms in the biofilm itself or living matter to disrupt their existence (Gule,
41 Begum, & Klumperman, 2016). Alternatively, cost-effective and environmentally-
42 friendly methods such as ultraviolet irradiation (Braga, 2018), ultrasound (Bott, 2000),
43 and electromagnetic fields (EMF) can be employed. These methods are non-toxic and
44 disturb biological growth (Boullosa-Falces, García, Sanz, Trueba, & Gomez-Solaetxe,
45 2020; Trueba, García, & Otero, 2014; Xiao et al., 2020; Xiao et al., 2021).
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53

54 Some predictive techniques have been investigated for monitoring biofilms inside heat
55 exchangers, such as neural networks (Tang, Li, Wang, He, & Tao, 2020), Kalman filters
56
57
58
59
60

1
2
3
4 (Sundar et al., 2020), and image-based monitoring (Tachtatzis et al., 2015), require a long
5 learning period and their use, are complex for the end user, and require a large number of
6 variables to be analysed, which are not available in the ship's standard data acquisition
7 equipment.
8
9

10
11 AI is an intelligent approach, which have demonstrated high performance in solving
12 environmental engineering problems (Bagheri, Akbari, & Mirbagheri, 2019). Some
13 authors (Gernaey, Van Loosdrecht, Henze, Lind, & Jørgensen, 2004; Schmitt & Do,
14 2017) have created AI-based models for managing activated sludge wastewater treatment
15 facilities to enhance and optimize the treatment process. In order to assist plant operators,
16 supervisory control systems have been designed with the objective of enhancing plant
17 efficiency and bolstering operational dependability through automation, wherein both AI
18 methodologies and mechanistic models play pivotal roles. Other author, Fan et al. (Fan,
19 Hu, Cao, Ruan, & Wei, 2018) provided a comprehensive overview of the utilization of
20 artificial intelligence techniques in experimental design for the removal of pollutants in
21 water treatment. These AI methods have been applied to model and optimize the removal
22 of pollutants in water treatment, resulting in the generation of optimal operational
23 parameters. The outcomes of these investigations validate the effective implementation
24 of hybrid models in water treatment, yielding satisfactory levels of accuracy.
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32

33
34 The research evaluated which AI value would best maintain the initial design conditions
35 of the heat transfer process while minimising the environment impact and energy
36 consumption. The main objective of this study is to develop an AI model addresses the
37 issue of optimising the antifouling biocide dose as a function of the loss thermal efficiency
38 in order minimise the environmental impact, reduce maintenance and operating cost. The
39 specific aims to be achieved during the experiment were as follows: (1) to allow a biofilm
40 to grow inside the heat exchanger until experimental variables indicated until the optimal
41 performance threshold is reached (2) to apply AI model with the statistical algorithm
42 developed to control heat exchanger treatment, (3) to qualitatively assess the AI operation
43 of heat exchanger, and (4) to quantify the influence of the energy consumption of
44 pumping equipment to maintain the equipment's hydraulic conditions. The scientific
45 relevance of this research stems from the development of AI for increasing thermal
46 effectiveness and productivity, and to reduce the environmental impact generated in the
47 biocide dosing processes in seawater cooling systems.
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Equipment for study

The equipment under study simulates the system cooling installed on power thermal plant and on board any ship. This system was composed of a tube heat exchanger which was cooled by seawater. The heat exchanger was monitored completely and data were analysed for AI decision making. AI technologies applied facilitated decision-making processing by analysing vast amounts of data, recognizing patterns, and taking optimal solutions.

2.1.1. Heat exchanger

The biofilm's behaviour underwent examination within a test facility, as depicted in Figure 1. This specific facility comprises cooling heat exchangers powered by seawater coursing through four distinct tubes, each measuring 3.1mm in length (with a diameter of 10.2 mm and a thickness of 2.5 mm). These tubes are constructed from AISI 316Ti-grade stainless steel, featuring composition specifications ($C \leq 0.080\%$; $Mn \leq 2.0\%$; $P \leq 0.045\%$; $S \leq 0.030\%$; $Si \leq 1\%$; $Cr 16.0\text{--}18.0\%$; $Mo 2.0\text{--}3.0\%$; $Ti 0.7\%$; $Ni 10.0\text{--}14.0\%$; $N \leq 0.1\%$; Fe Balance %; N6 class surface roughness). Adhering to the A270 standard, the tubes boast a surface roughness of $0.8 \mu\text{m}$. Conforming to guidelines established by the Tubular Exchanger Manufacturers Association (TEMA), the heat exchanger was meticulously designed and manufactured. The exchanger's shell, crafted from AISI 304 stainless steel, possessed an outer diameter of 240 mm and a thickness of 20 mm. To curtail energy dissipation, a 40 mm layer of glass wool insulation ($k=0.038 \text{ W m } ^\circ\text{C}$) enveloped the heat exchanger's shell (Agyenim, Eames, & Smyth, 2009).

2.1.2. Cooling systems

Two centrifugal pumps (model ITUR AU-MI 1.5/10, Zarautz, Spain) were used to draw seawater from the bay of Santander at a depth of four meters. The pumps were set up in series to ensure efficient water suction. The seawater intake was equipped with a 5 mm mesh filter to stop small particles like algae from entering and reaching the pump intake. The seawater was conveyed to a settling tank with a capacity of 1 m^3 of water. In this tank, sand and other heavy particles were settle down to the bottom of the tank. After the seawater was settled in the tank, it flowed to a service tank that had the same capacity as

1
2
3
4 the settling tank. Before being pumped at 1.9 bar, the water underwent another filtration
5 process with 0.5 mm mesh size used to remove small suspended particles. Two centrifugal
6 pumps (Grundfos CHI 4-50 A WG, Algete, Spain) were installed in parallel to push the
7 filtered seawater through the tubes that went through the heat exchangers, where it was
8 used as a cooling medium for the primary fluid.
9

10
11
12
13 The natural seawater was characterized through the analysis of the physical–chemical
14 properties of seawater during the experimental, obtained measures of pH value at 8.00 to
15 8.14, conductivity at 54.2 to 57.01 mS cm⁻¹ and oxygen dissolved at 8.4 to 8.5 mg/l. The
16 seawater was subject to monitoring both before and after passing through the heat
17 exchangers. The measuring equipment underwent adjustments and calibration beforehand
18 to ensure accuracy during the experiments. During the experiment, the flow velocity of
19 seawater was adjusted to 1 ms⁻¹ using variable frequency drives (variable-speed drive
20 Altivar312/2,2 kW/3 CV, Model: ATV312HU22N4. Schneider Electric. Rueil-
21 Malmaison, France). This was necessary because biofilm adhesion in the flow tube of the
22 heat exchanger caused flow losses and constriction, and the adjustment helped to
23 counteract these effects. To control the velocity of the fluid passing through the tubes, a
24 positive displacement flow transmitter (Badger Meter M25 PFT-420 Badger Meter
25 Europe, Neuffen, Germany) was employed. At the inlet and outlet of the heat exchanger,
26 pressure difference meters (PTX 2170-1656, Sensocon Inc., Highland City, FL, USA)
27 and resistance thermometers (Surface Mount RTD 100 Ω DIN Class A, Sedem. SA.,
28 Barcelona, Spain) were installed. Once the seawater passed through the heat exchangers
29 in an open circuit, it was then discharged back into the sea.
30
31

32
33
34
35 The heat exchanger was equipped with a closed circuit, through which the water that
36 needed to be cooled circulated. A circulation pump (Grundfos MG90SA4-24F 1151IP
37 44CLF, Algete, Spain) was utilized to send water through this circuit at a pressure of 0.5
38 bar, after which it was directed to a mixing tank. The temperature of the mixing tank was
39 kept constant at 36°C. To maintain this temperature, the water was continuously
40 circulated to a heat exchanger (UFX-26H Sedical. Vizcaya, Spain), where it acquired
41 energy from water at a temperature of 80°C that was coming from the boilers. To supply
42 the necessary energy and maintain a temperature of 36°C, an automatic proportional-
43 integral-derivative (PID) control system (OMRON E5CK, Omron Electronics Iberia,
44 Madrid, Spain) and a 3-way valve were utilized. The flow rate of the water that needed
45 to be cooled was set to 17 m³ with the aid of a rotameter-type flow meter.
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

2.1.3. Biocide Treatment

The heat exchanger features a dedicated dosing circuit (see Figure 1), consisting of a dosing pump equipped with a dry electromagnetic membrane, adjustable speed, and stroke (DOSAPRO MILTON ROY® model LMI P1. Houston, Texas, USA). This pump draws from its designated biocide storage tank (5 liters). Programming of the dosing intervals was accomplished using a time switch (Theben® model SUL180. Haigerloch, Germany), capable of setting various time frequencies throughout a 24-hour period. The biocide was sodium hypochlorite (NaOCl) which is a conventional biocide obtained from active chlorine (Cl_2) ($\geq 138 \text{ g kg}^{-1}$), sodium hydroxide (NaOH) ($\geq 2 \leq 8 \text{ g kg}^{-1}$), sodium carbonate (Na_2CO_3) ($\leq 16 \text{ g kg}^{-1}$), iron (Fe) ($\leq 2 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$) and H_2O (CAS number 7681-52-9). It is a yellowish-brown liquid and is oxidising in nature. Its density is $1,234 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$ ($20 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$), its $\text{pH} > 12$ and its boiling point is $120 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (Patm).

2.2. Experimental plan

Throughout the experiment, the efficacy of AI in preventing the formation of biofilms on the inner surfaces of heat exchanger cooled by seawater was assessed. The AI controlled the efficiency of heat exchanger to save-energy and reduce the environment impact. The experiment was conducted during the peak biological activity period (May–July 2021).

The study assessed how the presence of biofilm affects the transfer of heat in a heat exchanger when seawater is flowing through it. Prior to conducting the experiment, the heat exchanger underwent extensive cleaning to ensure an optimal starting condition.

Monitoring and data acquisition were performed using four configurable multifunction modules (STEP model DL01-CPU, STEP Logistics and Control, Barcelona, Spain) that monitored and stored 100% of the data in real-time. Throughout the experiment, the mean ambient temperature was 22°C , and the hydraulic conditions within each tube remained stable, with a flow velocity of 1 m/s and a constant flow rate of 4.8 l min^{-1} .

The biofilm was allowed to develop until the AI indicated that the heat exchanger is starting to become dirty beyond the optimum performance threshold. Subsequently, AI worked as illustrated in Figure 2. Following the flowchart of Figure 2, AI ordered to start the treatment phase which was intermittent maintenance (6 h on, 6 h off) with a dose of 0.5 ppm of biocide over 17 days, aimed at maintaining the conditions that were achieved during the first phase of treatment.

2.3. Uncertainty measurements

The primary components of the system error encompass three facets: data processing error, random error, and system device error. Among these, the data processing error emerges from equation calculations and can be disregarded in the ongoing experiment. Random errors can be minimized through multiple measurements. In assessing the uncertainty of each individual parameter, the precision of the measurement instrument was considered. The Equation 1 can be employed to establish the relative uncertainty of the indirectly measured value (García & Trueba, 2018):

$$W_R^+ = \left(\left(\frac{\delta R^+}{\delta X_1} w_1 \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\delta R^+}{\delta X_2} w_2 \right)^2 + \dots + \left(\frac{\delta R^+}{\delta X_n} w_n \right)^2 \right)^{1/2} \quad (1)$$

Each of these parameters corresponds to the distinct influence exerted by the uncertainty in a specific variable (w_n) on the comprehensive uncertainty of the overall outcome. In this context, W_R^+ represents the summation of the partial derivatives of R concerning the captured measurements (X_n), each multiplied by the respective w_n value for that particular parameter. The probability of the computed uncertainty enveloping the true value of the result mirrors the probability of individual measurement uncertainties encompassing their true values. Furthermore, deviations linked to the experimental parameters exhibited only minimal variations, which buttresses the authenticity and dependability of the findings. This fact becomes evident upon scrutinizing the data presented in Table 1.

2.4. Normal distribution of samples

IBM SPSS Statistics software was used to perform statistical analyses of the samples. Normal distribution was tested by examining Q-Q plots based on the beta distribution. Since the observed data fell within the anticipated beta values (Castillo-Gutiérrez & Aguilera, 2007), the hypothesis of normality of the data was supported. This allowed the statistical algorithm to be applied to the data.

2.5. Biofilm Prediction Network Architecture

The key component of the algorithm is a neural network architecture that takes in operating conditions data of tubular heat exchanger as its in/output data and performance

1
2
3
4 predict in function of biofilm resistances. The cornerstone of the algorithm revolves
5 around a neural network architecture, which leverages operational data from tubular heat
6 exchangers as both its input and output. Its primary function lies in predicting
7 performance variations based on biofouling resistances. This overarching approach holds
8 universal applicability across diverse heat exchangers. The neural network is fuelled by
9 several inputs, including initial fluid temperatures (T_i), flow rates (\dot{m}), differential
10 pressure differentials across the inflow and outflow, as well as outlet fluid temperatures
11 (T_o). In an industrial setting, acquiring these data poses no challenge, as they can be
12 readily measured through the deployment of fluid temperature and flow rate sensors at
13 the entry and exit points of the pipes.
14
15
16
17
18
19

20
21 Two methods were used to track the formation of biofilm on the inner surfaces of the heat
22 exchanger tubes. Firstly, an AI model was employed to monitor the flow rate of seawater
23 flowing through the heat exchanger. Secondly, the variable R_f (heat transfer resistance),
24 which indicates the sum of the resistances to heat transfer due to convective and
25 conduction mechanisms (García, Trueba, Vega, & Madariaga, 2016), widely used for this
26 purpose, was used.
27
28
29

30 2.5.1. Heat transfer resistance

31
32
33 The heat transfer resistance (R_f [$\text{m}^2 \text{K kW}^{-1}$]) is a measure that combines the conductive
34 and advective heat transfer resistances. Conductive heat transfer resistance arises due to
35 the transfer of heat from a higher temperature region to a lower temperature region within
36 a liquid or solid material. This transfer occurs because of the motion of molecules and
37 electrons in the material. It increased with the addition of the insulating layers formed by
38 the accumulated biofilm. The advective heat transfer resistance is the result of the heat
39 transport of heat caused by fluid movement. This resistance is reduced when there is
40 turbulence at the interface between the fluid and the surface, which is often caused by the
41 presence of biofilm. The total heat transfer resistance was calculated using Equation 2
42 (Trueba, Otero, González, Vega, & García, 2013).
43
44
45
46
47
48
49

$$50 R_f = \frac{A_{in}}{m_c \rho_c C_{p,c} \ln \left(\frac{T_{h,i} - T_{c,o}}{T_{h,o} - T_{c,i}} \right)} \quad (2)$$

51 2.5.2. Pumping energy losses

Analyzing and designing heat exchanger systems requires accurately determining the energy losses caused by biofilm adhesion. One aspect of this analysis involves tracking the evolution of the frictional resistance resulting from the biofilm adhesion in the inner tube of the heat exchanger. This is often done using indirect measurements obtained through a method that utilizes fluid transport properties (García et al., 2016). The fluid frictional resistance (f [dimensionless]) was calculated using Equation 3 (Boulloussa-Falces, Gomez-Solaetxe, García, Trueba, & Sanz, 2021):

$$f = \frac{2d\Delta p}{L\rho v^2} \quad (3)$$

The evaluating energy usage of centrifugal pump was developed although the kW usage was determined using a kilowatt meter (Fluke 345 Power Quality Clamp Meter-Electronic Power Meter, Eindhoven, Netherlands).

2.5.3. Artificial Intelligence

To evaluate the build-up of biofilm on the tube walls, an algorithm was used to track the seawater flow. Table 2 displays the statistical values for the recorded seawater flow rates.

The AI model based in a statistical algorithm (Montgomery, 2009) operates by accumulating deviations from each observation that are approximately the target value μ_0 with the statistic C^+ and accumulating deviations from each observation below the target value μ_0 with another statistic C^- . The statistics C^+ and C^- are called one-sided upper and lower CUSUM, respectively, and they have the following form:

$$C_i^+ = \max[0, X_i - (\mu_0 + K) + C_{i-1}^+] \quad (4)$$

$$C_i^- = \max[0, (\mu_0 - K) - X_i + C_{i-1}^-] \quad (5)$$

Where the starting values $C_0^+ = C_0^- = 0$

The equation used to calculate the reference value K , which defines the level of sensitivity of the statistical algorithm, is as follows:

$$K = k \delta \sigma_0 \quad (6)$$

where k is a tabulated value, typically a value of 0.5 is accepted; σ_0 is the standard deviation of the process under control, and δ represents the change in the mean of the standard deviations. This value can be variable and depends on the chosen δ value and

1
2
3
4 the value of K from which the deviation of the cumulative sum is considered significant,
5 making the method stringent.
6

7
8 The Average Run Length (ARL) determines the minimum number of samples needed to
9 avoid committing a false positive or false negative. Different ARL values (250, 375, 500,
10 625, 750, and 875) were analysed for the δ values of 1, 2, and 3. The value of $\delta = 1$ was
11 chosen carefully as the algorithm proved to be too strict with (2 / 3) values for δ and did
12 not detect appreciable changes in the monitored variable.
13
14

15
16 The decision interval H establishes the limit at which the control needs to be implemented
17 and is determined by the following equation:
18

$$H = h \delta \sigma_0 \quad (7)$$

19
20 where h is a tabulated value based on the average run length (ARL0) and k , the relevant
21 tables for which can be found in the literature (Hawkins & Olwell, 2012), and σ_0 is the
22 standard deviation of the process targeted for control. When the value of C_i^+ or C_i^- exceeds
23 the value of H , the process is considered out of control.
24
25
26
27
28
29
30

31 **3. Results and Discussion**

32 3.1. Evolution of biofilm growth.

33
34 The evolution of the Rf measurements followed a sigmoidal curve defined by Garcia et
35 al. (García & Trueba, 2018). As shown in Figure 3, the progress of Rf shows the three
36 phases of biofilm growth: induction phase (day 0–10), exponential growth phase (day 10–
37 44) and levelling-off phase (day 44–60). The induction phase developed during the first
38 10 days of the experiment, during which heat transfer losses were insignificant. Next, the
39 exponential growth phase occurred when the biofilm was attached to the surface tubes of
40 the heat exchanger, causing the heat transfer losses to increase. Finally, the biofilm
41 adhesion on the heat exchanger was sufficiently significant to consider that the equipment
42 was working off-design, and it was necessary to begin the process of cleaning. The Rf
43 measurements recorded an average increase over the initial values of 41%. Previous
44 research has indicated that the increase in the values of Rf is a consequence of the thermal
45 resistance provided by convection and conduction. (Boullosa-Falces, Sanz, Garcia,
46 Trueba-Castañeda, & Trueba, 2022; Trueba, Vega, García, Otero, & Madariaga, 2016).
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55

56 3.2. Analysis on energy consumption

57
58
59
60

1
2
3
4 The Figure 4 shows that the fluid frictional resistance (f) follows a characteristic
5 sigmoidal curve for the tested heat exchanger, as defined in previous research (García et
6 al., 2016; García & Trueba, 2018). Decreasing f values were obtained initially as biofilm
7 deposits filled the rough cavities and smoothed the tube wall. However, on day 20 and
8 thereafter, biofilm accumulation caused a pronounced increase in f with an increase in the
9 roughness of the support medium and a decrease in the effective diameter of the tube. At
10 the 43 day of the experiment, the average increase in f over the initial value was 113%.
11 The f increased caused energy consumption growth, and the costs of the pumping
12 equipment to maintain the equipment's hydraulic conditions. When f reached its peak
13 performance level on day 43, the application of a shock treatment involving 0.5 ppm of
14 NaOCl resulted in an average decrease of 76.6% in Δf . The duration of the shock
15 treatment with NaOCl was 3 days. Throughout this period, chlorine was conveyed
16 through the liquid to the interface between the biofilm and water, where it was released
17 and reacted with the cells and chemical compounds in the liquid serving as reducing
18 agents.
19

20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28 The power consumption of pumping showed an increase of 9% with a sigmoidal-shaped
29 growth trend similar to the curve of frictional resistance (Figure 4). The performance heat
30 exchanger accounted for additional pumping energy costs of approximately € 0.57 per
31 kWh at the end of the experiment. Energy costs were based on operating 24 h a day, 43
32 days of experimentation (1032 h) at a presumed cost of € 0.34 per kWh.
33
34
35
36

37 3.3. Evaluation the performance of AI model developed

38
39 Equations (4) and (5) were used to monitor the seawater flow variable for different values
40 of δ and ARLO. $\delta = 1$ is the best fit for the real model. Table 3 presents the mean and
41 standard deviation (SD) of the flow rate in the ARLO, control, and treated samples for
42 different values of ARL. The results are presented in Figures 5–10.
43
44
45

46 As shown in Figure 5, for an ARLO of 250, it can be seen that the variable remains
47 practically constant until sample 780, where a reduction in flow rate generated by the
48 fouling of the biofilm begins to occur. Thus, the CUSUM algorithm detects that the heat
49 exchanger is starting to become dirty beyond the optimum performance threshold, and
50 starts to progressively decrease until sample 820, where it exceeds the established limit,
51 indicating that since day 44 (1070 hourly samples since the experiment began), the heat
52 exchanger is not operating under optimal operating conditions.
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

1
2
3
4 For a chosen ARLO of 375, in Figure 6, it can be seen that the algorithm remains
5 practically constant until sample 655, at which it starts to decrease until it exceeds the
6 control limit H, at a value of -0.43. At this point, the heat exchanger can be considered to
7 have passed the normal operation phase. This limit is exceeded at sample 667.
8 Considering ARLO 375, the moment when the experiment began, it was deduced that the
9 limit is crossed on day 43.
10
11

12
13
14 On the other hand, when 500 initial samples are considered as ARLO, the statistic behaves
15 in a similar way; they have a constant behaviour above the control limit until reaching
16 sample 520, when the statistic slowly decreases until exceeds the limit at hourly sample
17 535, that is, 1035 hourly samples. This means that, for 43 days, according to the
18 algorithm, the heat exchanger behaved within the established margins of optimal
19 operating conditions.
20
21
22

23
24 On the other hand, when an ARLO of 625 is established, the deviation in the process is
25 detected at observation 408. As with the other ARLO analysed, it is after 43 days when
26 the biofilm starts to foul, causing the heat exchanger to not work under optimum operating
27 conditions and this indicate that actions have to be carried out for the correct operation of
28 the heat exchanger.
29
30
31

32
33 Finally, with ARLO 750 and 875, the process behaves similarly to the cases analysed
34 above and the statistic has a constant trajectory above the control limit; that is, the heat
35 exchanger is not sufficiently dirty to indicate that action is necessary. Subsequently, the
36 monitored variable drops at samples 281 and 156 for ARLO 750 and 875, respectively;
37 that is, 43 days after the last cleaning of the equipment, indicating that fouling due to
38 biofilm adhering to the inner walls of the tube has caused a decrease in the seawater flow
39 rate, reducing the heat transfer of the heat exchanger to below normal operating
40 conditions. Table 4 summarises the results obtained from the statistical modelling.
41
42
43
44

45
46 After the analysis of the CUSUM graphs in Figures 5–10, it can observe that with all the
47 ARLOs used, the monitored variable exceeds the control limit at 43–44 days from the
48 beginning of the experiment, that is, after the last cleaning of the heat exchanger. This is
49 an advantage compared to other methods (Boullosa-Falces, Gomez-Solaetxe, Sanchez-
50 Varela, García, & Trueba, 2019) because a large number of samples is not necessary for
51 the algorithm to work.
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

1
2
3
4 On the other hand, unlike other studies carried out (Boullousa-Falces et al., 2020) in which
5 the temperature difference between the inlet and outlet of the seawater was monitored,
6 the monitoring of the flow rate is more conservative and less predictive, which means that
7 the user has more operating time before having to carry out maintenance work. In fact, it
8 indicates that the process exceeds the control limit two days before the levelling-off
9 phase, when maintenance must be carried out.
10
11

12 13 14 **4. Conclusions**

15
16 Proper monitoring of exchanger conditions is crucial to help make operational decisions
17 regarding biofilm mitigation options and cleaning strategies, as well as to detect and
18 diagnose unexpected events and help plan corrective actions.
19
20

21
22 The Rf monitoring indicate the growth phases of the biofilm which certificate that the AI
23 model take decision properly.
24

25
26 Biofilm adhesion of the fluid through a tube significantly affects the friction resistance,
27 which significantly increases the cost of the pumping operation of the heat exchanger.
28 Proper monitoring using a statistical algorithm for efficiency control in heat exchangers
29 is financially feasible if the price difference can be offset later by a reduction in energy
30 losses.
31
32

33
34 The AI model developed is effective to the biofilm formation control on the tube surface
35 of a heat exchanger because it monitors, analyse and order actions when a heat exchanger
36 had become dirty beyond the optimum performance threshold. Current monitoring
37 systems that use Artificial-intelligence-algorithm to control the evolution of the biofilm
38 have a very highly sensitive predictive character, often indicating too far in advance that
39 cleaning of the exchanger is necessary or biocide dosing, when in reality the equipment
40 could be operating at maximum performance for several weeks.
41
42
43
44

45
46 AI represents an efficient alternative to minimize the environment impact of highly toxic
47 biocides in a marine medium. AI use as an AF method allowed reduce the environment
48 impact and the elimination of a mature biofilm that adhered to the tubes of a heat
49 exchanger that was cooled by seawater and for the recovery of the initial efficiency of the
50 heat transfer process to practically clean conditions.
51
52
53

54
55 This Artificial-intelligence-algorithm can be implemented in anyway power thermal plant
56 for the current monitoring systems. This new AI model can help to optimize the cost
57
58
59
60

operation, technical and environmental aspects in anyway heat transfer process in most chemical processing industries, including oil refining, pulp and paper manufacturing, polymer and fibre production, desalination, food processing, dairy industries, ships, power generation and energy recovery.

Funding

This study was funded by projects IT1514-22 and EUIN2017-89002.

Nomenclature

A	surface of tube wall, m ²
ARLO	average run length
C	deviation
CUSUM	cumulative Cusum charts
AF	antifouling
C _p	specific heat at constant pressure, J kg ⁻¹ K ⁻¹
d	diameter, m
H	control limit of CUSUM charts
h	tabulated value from ARLO and k
K	reference value which the cumulative deviation is considered to be significant
k	tabulated value, typical value of 0.5
L	tube length, m
ṁ	water mass flow rate, kg s ⁻¹
P	power device, W
Q	Seawater flow rate (Q), l/min
R	overall uncertainty in the result
R _f	heat transfer resistance without treatment, m ² K W ⁻¹
T	fluid temperature, K
v	velocity flow, m s ⁻¹
w	independent uncertainty in the measurement
W	total uncertainty in the measurement
X	independent variable

Greek symbols

ρ	seawater density, kg m ⁻³
σ ₀	standard deviation
μ ₀	objective value
Δp	differential pressure, Pa

Subscripts

c	cold
---	------

1
2
3
4 h hot
5 i inlet
6 o outlet
7
8
9

10 **References**

- 13 Agyenim, F., Eames, P., & Smyth, M. 2009. A comparison of heat transfer
14 enhancement in a medium temperature thermal energy storage heat exchanger
15 using fins. *Solar Energy*. 83(9): 1509-1520. doi: [10.1016/j.solener.2009.04.007](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2009.04.007)
16
17
18
19 Al-Bloushi, M., Saththasivam, J., Jeong, S., Al-Refaie, A., Kumar, R. S. A., Ng, K. C.,
20 Leiknes, T. 2020. An investigation into the efficiency of biocides in controlling
21 algal biofouling in seawater industrial cooling towers. 26(6): 190397. doi:
22 10.4491/eer.2019.397
23
24
25
26 Bagheri, M., Akbari, A., & Mirbagheri, S. A. 2019. Advanced control of membrane
27 fouling in filtration systems using artificial intelligence and machine learning
28 techniques: A critical review. *Process Safety and Environmental Protection*. 123:
29 229-252. doi: [10.1016/j.psep.2019.01.013](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psep.2019.01.013)
30
31
32
33
34 Bott, T. R. 2000. Biofouling control with ultrasound. *Heat Transfer Engineering*. 21(3):
35 43-49. doi: [10.1080/014576300270898](https://doi.org/10.1080/014576300270898)
36
37
38
39 Bouldosa-Falces, D., Gomez-Solaetxe, M. A., García, S., Trueba, A., & Sanz, D. 2021.
40 Biofouling control in heat exchangers by statistical techniques. *Developments in*
41 *maritime technology and engineering*. pp. 737-742 CRC Press. doi:
42 10.1201/9781003216582-83
43
44
45
46 Bouldosa-Falces, D., García, S., Sanz, D., Trueba, A., & Gomez-Solaetxe, M. A. 2020.
47 CUSUM chart method for continuous monitoring of antifouling treatment of
48 tubular heat exchangers in open-loop cooling seawater systems. *Biofouling*. 36(1):
49 73-85. doi: [10.1080/08927014.2020.1715954](https://doi.org/10.1080/08927014.2020.1715954)
50
51
52
53 Bouldosa-Falces, D., Gomez-Solaetxe, M. A., Sanchez-Varela, Z., García, S., & Trueba,
54 A. 2019. Validation of CUSUM control chart for biofouling detection in heat
55
56
57
58
59
60

- 1
2
3
4 exchangers. *Applied Thermal Engineering*. 152: 24-31. doi:
5 [10.1016/j.applthermaleng.2019.02.009](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applthermaleng.2019.02.009)
6
7
8
9
10 Bouldosa-Falces, D., Sanz, D. S., Garcia, S., Trueba-Castañeda, L., & Trueba, A. 2022.
11 Predicting tubular heat exchanger efficiency reduction caused by marine biofilm
12 adhesion using CFD simulations. *Biofouling*. 38(7): 663-673. doi:
13 [10.1080/08927014.2022.2110493](https://doi.org/10.1080/08927014.2022.2110493)
14
15
16 Braga, C. R. 2018. *Lighting a Path to Biofouling Prevention: Investigating the Effect of*
17 *Ultraviolet Light on Biofouling*. [Masters Thesis]. Florida Institute of
18 Technology.USA.
19
20
21
22 Brzozowska, A. M., Parra-Velandia, F. J., Quintana, R., Xiaoying, Z., Lee, S. S., Chin-
23 Sing, L. Vancso, J. G. 2014. Biomimicking micropatterned surfaces and their effect
24 on marine biofouling. *Langmuir*. 30(30): 9165-9175. doi: 10.1021/la502006s
25
26
27 Castillo-Gutiérrez, S., & Aguilera, E. D. L. 2007. QQ plot normal. los puntos de
28 posición gráfica. *Iniciación a La Investigación*, (2), 8.
29 <https://revistaselectronicas.ujaen.es/index.php/ininv/article/view/259/241>
30
31
32
33 Chan, J., & Wong, S. 2010. *Biofouling: Types, impact and anti-fouling* Nova Science
34 Publishers, Incorporated.
35
36
37 Demirskiy, O. V., Kapustenko, P. O., Arsenyeva, O. P., Matsegora, O. I., & Pugach, Y.
38 A. 2018. Prediction of fouling tendency in PHE by data of on-site monitoring. case
39 study at sugar factory. *Applied Thermal Engineering*. 128: 1074-1081. doi:
40 [10.1016/j.applthermaleng.2017.09.087](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applthermaleng.2017.09.087)
41
42
43
44 Eguía, E., Trueba, A., Río-Calonge, B., Girón, A., & Bielva, C. 2008. Biofilm control in
45 tubular heat exchangers refrigerated by seawater using flow inversion physical
46 treatment. *International Biodeterioration & Biodegradation*. 62(2): 79-87. doi:
47 [10.1016/j.ibiod.2007.12.004](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ibiod.2007.12.004)
48
49
50
51
52 Fan, M., Hu, J., Cao, R., Ruan, W., & Wei, X. 2018. A review on experimental design
53 for pollutants removal in water treatment with the aid of artificial intelligence.
54 *Chemosphere*. 200: 330-343. doi: 10.1016/j.chemosphere.2018.02.111.
55
56
57
58
59
60

1
2
3
4 FitrIDGE, I., Dempster, T., Guenther, J., & De Nys, R. 2012. The impact and control of
5 biofouling in marine aquaculture: A review. *Biofouling*. 28(7): 649-669. doi:
6 [10.1016/j.chemosphere.2018.02.111](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2018.02.111)
7
8

9
10 García, S., & Trueba, A. 2018. Influence of the Reynolds number on the thermal
11 effectiveness of tubular heat exchanger subjected to electromagnetic field-based
12 antifouling treatment in an open once-through seawater cooling system. *Applied*
13 *Thermal Engineering*. 140: 531-541. doi: [10.1016/j.applthermaleng.2018.05.069](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applthermaleng.2018.05.069)
14
15

16
17 García, S., Trueba, A., Vega, L. M., & Madariaga, E. 2016. Impact of the surface
18 roughness of AISI 316L stainless steel on biofilm adhesion in a seawater-cooled
19 tubular heat exchanger-condenser. *Biofouling*. 32(10): 1185-1193. doi:
20 [10.1080/08927014.2016.1241875](https://doi.org/10.1080/08927014.2016.1241875)
21
22

23
24 Gaudio, M. T., Coppola, G., Zangari, L., Curcio, S., Greco, S., & Chakraborty, S. 2021.
25 Artificial intelligence-based optimization of industrial membrane processes. *Earth*
26 *Systems and Environment*. 5(2): 385-398. doi: [10.1007/s41748-021-00220-x](https://doi.org/10.1007/s41748-021-00220-x)
27
28

29
30 Gernaey, K. V., Van Loosdrecht, M. C., Henze, M., Lind, M., & Jørgensen, S. B. 2004.
31 Activated sludge wastewater treatment plant modelling and simulation: State of the
32 art. *Environmental Modelling & Software*. 19(9): 763-783. doi:
33 [10.1016/j.envsoft.2003.03.005](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsoft.2003.03.005)
34
35

36
37 Gudmundsson, O., Palsson, O. P., Palsson, H., & Lalot, S. 2016. Online fouling
38 detection of domestic hot water heat exchangers. *Heat Transfer Engineering*.
39 37(15): 1231-1241. doi: [10.1080/01457632.2015.1119584](https://doi.org/10.1080/01457632.2015.1119584)
40
41

42
43 Gule, N. P., Begum, N. M., & Klumperman, B. 2016. Advances in biofouling
44 mitigation: A review. *Critical Reviews in Environmental Science and Technology*.
45 46(6): 535-555. doi: [10.1080/10643389.2015.1114444](https://doi.org/10.1080/10643389.2015.1114444)
46
47

48
49 Hawkins, D. M., & Olwell, D. H. 2012. *Cumulative sum charts and charting for quality*
50 *improvement* Springer Science & Business Media.
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

- 1
2
3
4 Hu, P., Xie, Q., Ma, C., & Zhang, G. 2020. Silicone-based fouling-release coatings for
5 marine antifouling. *Langmuir*. 36(9): 2170-2183. doi:
6 10.1021/acs.langmuir.9b03926
7
8
9
10 Montgomery, D. C. 2009. Introduction to statistical quality control John Wiley & Sons
11 (New York).
12
13
14 Olufade, A. O., & Simonson, C. J. 2018. Application of indirect non-invasive methods
15 to detect the onset of crystallization fouling in a liquid-to-air membrane energy
16 exchanger. *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer*. 127: 663-673. doi:
17 10.1016/j.ijheatmasstransfer.2018.06.032
18
19
20
21 Rice, D., Rajwade, K., Zuo, K., Bansal, R., Li, Q., Garcia-Segura, S., & Perreault, F.
22 2021. Electrochemically-active carbon nanotube coatings for biofouling mitigation:
23 Cleaning kinetics and energy consumption for cathodic and anodic regimes.
24 *Journal of Colloid and Interface Science*. 603: 391-397. doi:
25 10.1016/j.jcis.2021.06.090
26
27
28
29
30
31 Schmitt, F., & Do, K. 2017. Prediction of membrane fouling using artificial neural
32 networks for wastewater treated by membrane bioreactor technologies: Bottlenecks
33 and possibilities. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*. 24(29): 22885-
34 22913. doi: 10.1007/s11356-017-0046-7
35
36
37
38 Silva, E. R., Ferreira, O., Ramalho, P. A., Azevedo, N. F., Bayón, R., Igartua, A.,
39 Calhorda, M. J. 2019. Eco-friendly non-biocide-release coatings for marine
40 biofouling prevention. *Science of the Total Environment*. 650: 2499-2511. doi:
41 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2018.10.010
42
43
44
45 Sundar, S., Rajagopal, M. C., Zhao, H., Kuntumalla, G., Meng, Y., Chang, H. C., Sinha,
46 S. 2020. Fouling modeling and prediction approach for heat exchangers using deep
47 learning. *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer*. 159: 120112. doi:
48 10.1016/j.ijheatmasstransfer.2020.120112
49
50
51
52 Tachtatzis, C., Sheridan, R., Michie, C., Atkinson, R. C., Cleary, A., Dziewierz, J.,
53 Sefcik, J. 2015. Image-based monitoring for early detection of fouling in
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

- 1
2
3
4 crystallisation processes. *Chemical Engineering Science*.133: 82-90. doi:
5 [10.1016/j.ces.2015.01.038](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ces.2015.01.038)
6
7
8
9 Tang, S., Li, M., Wang, F., He, Y., & Tao, W. 2020. Fouling potential prediction and
10 multi-objective optimization of a flue gas heat exchanger using neural networks
11 and genetic algorithms. *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer*. 152:
12 119488. doi: [10.1016/j.ijheatmasstransfer.2020.119488](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheatmasstransfer.2020.119488)
13
14
15 Trueba, A., García, S., & Otero, F. M. 2014. Mitigation of biofouling using
16 electromagnetic fields in tubular heat exchangers—condensers cooled by seawater.
17 *Biofouling*. 30(1): 95-103. doi: [10.1080/08927014.2013.847926](https://doi.org/10.1080/08927014.2013.847926)
18
19
20 Trueba, A., Otero, F. M., González, J. A., Vega, L. M., & García, S. 2013. Study of the
21 activity of quaternary ammonium compounds in the mitigation of biofouling in
22 heat exchangers—condensers cooled by seawater. *Biofouling*. 29(9): 1139-1151.
23 doi: [10.1080/08927014.2013.830108](https://doi.org/10.1080/08927014.2013.830108)
24
25
26 Trueba, A., Vega, L. M., García, S., Otero, F. M., & Madariaga, E. 2016. Mitigation of
27 marine biofouling on tubes of open rack vaporizers using electromagnetic fields.
28 *Water Science and Technology*. 73(5):1221-1229. doi: [10.2166/wst.2015.597](https://doi.org/10.2166/wst.2015.597)
29
30
31 Xiao, Y., Liu, Y., Ma, C., Muhammad, T., Zhou, B., Zhou, Y., . . . Li, Y. 2021. Using
32 electromagnetic fields to inhibit biofouling and scaling in biogas slurry drip
33 irrigation emitters. *Journal of Hazardous Materials*. 401:123265. doi:
34 [10.1016/j.jhazmat.2020.123265](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2020.123265)
35
36
37 Xiao, Y., Seo, Y., Lin, Y., Li, L., Muhammad, T., Ma, C., & Li, Y. 2020.
38 Electromagnetic fields for biofouling mitigation in reclaimed water distribution
39 systems. *Water Research*. 173:115562. doi: [10.1016/j.watres.2020.115562](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2020.115562)
40
41
42 Xie, Q., Pan, J., Ma, C., & Zhang, G. 2019. Dynamic surface antifouling: Mechanism
43 and systems. *Soft Matter*.15(6): 1087-1107. doi: [10.1039/C8SM01853G](https://doi.org/10.1039/C8SM01853G)
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53

54 **List of Tables**

55 Table 1. Maximum uncertainty of parameters.
56
57
58
59
60

1
2
3
4 Table 2. Statistical values of seawater flow rate (Q).
5

6 Table 3. ARLO and new samples. Means and SDs.
7

8 Table 4. Resume of statistical algorithm.
9

10 11 12 **List of Figures**

13
14
15 Figure 1. Experimental setup plant.

16
17 Figure 2. Proposed approach for the advanced control of heat exchanger biofouling
18 using AI techniques.
19

20
21 Figure 3. Progression of heat transfer resistance

22
23 Figure 4. Evolution in the increase of frictional resistance and power pumping
24 consumption.
25

26
27 Figure 5. Algorithm (ARL 250)

28
29 Figure 6. Algorithm (ARL 375)

30
31 Figure 7. Algorithm (ARL 500)

32
33 Figure 8. Algorithm (ARL 625)

34
35 Figure 9. Algorithm (ARL 750)

36
37 Figure 10. Algorithm (ARL 875)
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

Table 1. Maximum uncertainty of parameters.

Parameter	Unit	Bias uncertainty
Hot water inlet temperature	K	± 0.5
Hot seawater outlet temperature	K	± 0.5
Cold seawater inlet temperature	K	± 0.5
Cold water outlet temperature	K	± 0.5
Diameter of tubes	mm	± 0.01
Hot water flow rate	m ³ h ⁻¹	± 0.07
Cold seawater flow rate	m ³ h ⁻¹	± 0.1
Heat transfer resistance	%	± 4,3
Uncertainty in reading values of table (Cp, ρ, etc.)	%	± 0.1–0.3

1
2
3
4 Table 2. Statistical values of seawater flow rate (Q).
5
6

Variable	Unit	Min. Value	Max. Value	Mean(μ)	Standard Deviation (σ)
Q	(l/min)	4.2	4.8	4.452	0.131

7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

Table 3. ARLO and new samples. Means and SDs.

		Seawater flow rate (Q). (l/min)	
		Means (μ)	SDs (σ)
ARL 250	ARLO	4.37	0.11
	New samples	4.47	0.13
ARL 375	ARLO	4.39	0.11
	New samples	4.47	0.13
ARL 500	ARLO	4.42	0.11
	New samples	4.47	0.14
ARL 625	ARLO	4.43	0.10
	New samples	4.47	0.15
ARL 750	ARLO	4.44	0.10
	New samples	4.47	0.15
ARL 875	ARLO	4.43	0.09
	New samples	4.48	0.17

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

Table 4. Resume of statistical algorithm.

	ARLO					
	250	375	500	625	750	875
Minimum number of samples to record a change in the process	820	667	535	408	281	156
Number of monitored samples before signalling	1070	1042	1035	1033	1031	1031
Detection day since last cleaning	44.5	43.4	43.1	43.04	42.9	42.9

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

Reviewers' Comments to Editor:

Dear Editor,

Thank you very much for accepting our manuscript for publication in Biofouling Journal.

The corrections in the manuscript are as following:

- All citations and references have been changed according to the journal's style, changing format and adding doi references.
- The email of authors has been added in page 1.
- It has been added other project in funding section.

Sincerely yours,

Prof. Dr. Sergio García